

LAPAROSCOPIC CHOLECYSTECTOMY IN ACUTE CHOLECYSTITIS IN PATIENTS WITH INCREASED OPERATIONAL RISK

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Purpose of the research. Improvement of surgical treatment results for acute calculous cholecystitis in patients with increased surgical risk.

Research material and methods.. Mat

This study is based on the analysis of clinical observations of 30 elderly and senile patients with acute calculous cholecystitis between 2017 and 2019. At the same time, the proportion of destructive forms of acute cholecystitis in elderly and senile patients is 50-58%. There were 3 (10%) men and 27 (90%) women aged 18 to 65. The duration of the disease ranged from 6 to 72 hours. All patients underwent surgery under general anesthesia under artificial lung ventilation, using an endovideosurgical stand. "Laparoscopic operations on the gallbladder were performed using an endosurgical complex and sets of surgical instruments from the Karl Storz company (Germany).

series and research methods..

Research results. LXE according to the technique optimized by us due to the combination of methods known to date. In the technique of performing the operation, we consider the following stages. LCHA was performed on 26 patients. In 3 patients, due to an infiltrate in the gallbladder neck area, an additional trocar was applied to the right hypochondrium, through which a puncture and aspiration of the gallbladder contents were performed, and subsequently, the subphrenic region was drained through this port. LCHE conversion was required in one patient, the reason being intraoperative bleeding. The average intervention time was 49 ± 6.1 min. No complications were observed in the early postoperative period. On the 2nd day, an ultrasound of the abdominal cavity was performed. Patients became active on the first day after surgery, the pain syndrome was minimal, and did not require the use of narcotic analgesics. Patients were discharged on the 5th day after surgery in satisfactory condition. The sutures were removed on an outpatient basis on the 5th day.

Conclusions. Laparoscopic cholecystectomy in elderly and senile patients allows for good results and, at the same time, reduces the invasiveness of surgical intervention and postoperative complications.

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